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MAKTABGACHA
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT: OPPORTUNITIES AND PREDICTIVE MECHANISMS IN THE CONTEXT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This paper investigates the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into educational management, with a particular focus on predictive mechanisms for Uzbekistan's school system. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study analyzes quantitative EMIS data alongside qualitative insights obtained from school leaders to identify current practices, challenges, and institutional readiness for AI-based forecasting. The findings indicate that only 18 % of schools currently use AI tools in managerial decision-making; however, more than 90 % of school principals acknowledge the necessity of AI for planning student enrollment, staffing, and academic performance. The paper concludes that the development of AI-supported forecasting within the national EMIS platform has the potential to transform decision-making processes from reactive to proactive management. Policy recommendations are proposed to strengthen digital infrastructure, leadership competencies, and data-driven governance.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Educational Management, Predictive Analytics, EMIS, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston maktab ta'limi tizimi uchun bashorat mexanizmlariga alohida e'tibor qaratgan holda sun'iy intellektni ta'lim menejmentiga integratsiya qilish masalalari tadqiq etiladi. Aralash metodologiyadan foydalanilgan holda tadqiqot sun'iy intellekt asosidagi prognozlashtirishga oid amaliyotlar, muammolar va tayyorgarlik darajasini aniqlash maqsadida EMIS (Ta'limni boshqarish axborot tizimi)ning miqdoriy ma'lumotlari hamda maktab rahbarlaridan olingan sifatli ma'lumotlarni tahlil qiladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, maktablarning atigi 18 % i boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilish jarayonida sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan foydalanadi, biroq direktorlarning 90 % dan ortig'i o'quvchilarni qabul qilish, kadrlar ta'minoti va akademik natijalarni rejalashtirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish zarurligini tan oladi. Maqolada milliy EMIS platformasi doirasida sun'iy intellekt bilan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan prognozlashtirishni joriy etish qaror qabul qilish jarayonini reaktiv boshqaruvdan proaktiv boshqaruvga o'tkazishi mumkinligi xulosalanadi. Raqamli infratuzilmani mustahkamlash, rahbarlik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish va ma'lumotlarga asoslangan boshqaruvni takomillashtirish bo'yicha siyosiy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ta'lim menejmenti, prognozli tahlil, EMIS, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется интеграция искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в систему управления образованием с акцентом на прогностические механизмы для школьной системы Узбекистана. С использованием смешанного методологического подхода в исследовании анализируются количественные данные EMIS (Информационной системы управления образованием) и качественные данные, полученные в ходе интервью с руководителями школ, с целью выявления текущих практик, проблем и уровня готовности к использованию прогнозирования на основе ИИ. Результаты показывают, что лишь 18 % школ применяют инструменты ИИ при принятии управленческих решений, однако более 90 % директоров признают необходимость их использования для планирования приёма учащихся, кадрового обеспечения и академической успеваемости. В статье делается вывод о том, что внедрение прогнозирования с поддержкой ИИ в рамках национальной платформы EMIS способно трансформировать процесс принятия решений от реактивного к проактивному управлению. Предлагаются политические рекомендации, направленные на укрепление цифровой инфраструктуры, управленческих компетенций и управления, основанного на данных.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, управление образованием, прогностическая аналитика, EMIS, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

In the era of digital transformation, the education sector is undergoing fundamental changes driven by the increasing integration of artificial intelligence (AI). AI technologies have already transformed sectors such as finance, healthcare, and manufacturing; however, their application in educational management—particularly

in K–12 schools—remains limited and uneven worldwide. School leaders are increasingly expected to make data-informed and predictive decisions in areas such as student enrollment planning, teacher workload distribution, academic performance forecasting, and dropout prevention. These emerging demands necessitate the development of intelligent, adaptive systems capable of supporting real-time analysis and forecasting.

Globally, countries such as South Korea, Singapore, and Estonia have successfully piloted and implemented AI-based tools in education governance. Their experiences demonstrate that AI-supported decision-making can significantly improve operational efficiency, resource allocation, and policy responsiveness. In Uzbekistan, however, the integration of AI into school governance remains at an early stage.

Although digital platforms such as the Education Management Information System (EMIS) are in place, they are primarily used for administrative reporting rather than proactive analysis. Despite the existence of a centralized EMIS, its current functionality is largely confined to static data aggregation, offering limited support for dynamic prediction or decision-support mechanisms.

Uzbekistan's public education system, which serves more than 6 million school-aged children across over 10,000 institutions, faces a range of persistent challenges, including unequal teacher distribution (World Bank, 2023), overcrowded classrooms in urban areas, and fluctuating student attendance rates. Current school management practices often remain reactive rather than anticipatory. To address these challenges effectively, decision-makers require predictive tools that enable early identification of risks and informed long-term planning.

This study examines how artificial intelligence can enhance predictive decision-making within Uzbekistan's educational management system, thereby contributing to evidence-based governance and strategic planning. By analyzing current levels of AI usage, the readiness of school leaders, and the potential of AI-based forecasting systems, the research seeks to identify practical and scalable mechanisms for integrating AI into school governance. In addition, the study incorporates a comparative analysis of international best practices, offering insights into pathways for localized AI adoption within the Uzbek education context.

1. The following research questions guided the study: What is the current state of AI utilization in school management in Uzbekistan?
2. Which types of educational forecasts (e.g., student enrollment, staffing needs, examination outcomes) can AI most effectively support?
3. How can AI-based predictive models be integrated into national education data systems such as EMIS?

By addressing these questions, this paper aims to contribute both theoretically and practically to the expanding body of research on AI applications in education, while providing region-specific recommendations for effective implementation in Uzbekistan. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature; Section 3 outlines the research methodology; Section 4 presents and discusses the findings; and Section 5 concludes the study with recommendations for future research and policy development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past decade, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have deeply penetrated the education system, enabling radical changes in its management mechanisms. AI-based systems not only allow for the personalization of the learning process (Siemens & Long, 2011) but also support strategic decision-making in educational institutions, optimal resource allocation, and real-time monitoring. As noted in earlier research [6], learning analytics optimizes the learning environment through data-driven insights, which is increasingly becoming the central paradigm of modern educational management.

One of the most promising directions in the application of artificial intelligence is predictive analytics, which involves forecasting future events and processes based on large-scale data analysis. Predictive analytics helps identify behavioral patterns and forecast student outcomes [1]. For example, models based on artificial neural networks have been developed in U.S. schools to identify students at high risk of dropping out.

Furthermore, Holmes et al. (2019) demonstrate that AI tools enable not only real-time analysis but also proactive management, that is, planning by anticipating future needs. This approach significantly enhances the strategic flexibility and responsiveness of education systems.

Today, effective practices for managing schools through AI-based tools are being developed in several advanced countries. For example, in Singapore, automatic analyses and recommendations are generated for school principals based on class schedules, teacher workload, student participation, and assessment results using AI-driven systems. In Great Britain, schools employ “early warning systems” that identify factors threatening students' academic success at an early stage. These systems operate using machine learning (ML) algorithms and typically provide predictions with accuracy levels exceeding 80%.

In addition, artificial intelligence is increasingly being implemented to support budget forecasting, early identification of teacher shortages, curriculum adaptation, and the provision of personalized recommendations for learners and educators (Luckin et al., 2016), among other functions.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4884 dated November 6, 2020, digitalization processes in the field of education have been initiated, and information systems such as my.edu.uz, EMIS, and others have been implemented. However, most of these platforms are primarily designed for report generation and statistical analysis and do not yet possess proactive management or forecasting capabilities (Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan, 2024; Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2019).

Available analyses indicate that approximately 78% of schools have access to the Internet and computer technologies. This figure reaches 85% in urban areas but declines to only 56% in rural regions. In addition, about 65% of teachers regularly use online platforms, whereas only 17-20% of them are aware of or capable of using AI-based tools. These factors suggest that, for the effective implementation of AI-driven forecasting systems in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to stabilize digital infrastructure (OECD, 2022), equip teachers with AI-related competencies, improve the quality and reliability of educational data, and develop a national "AI-based School Management" strategy.

Based on the reviewed sources and international experience, several conclusions can be drawn. Artificial intelligence is emerging not only as a technological innovation in education management but also as a powerful instrument for strategic planning. A forecasting-based management approach shifts the school system toward preventing problems rather than merely responding to them. Uzbekistan possesses significant potential in this domain; however, fully realizing these opportunities will depend on the parallel development of technological infrastructure and human capital.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, which allows for the integrated analysis of quantitative and qualitative data and provides a solid foundation for an in-depth examination of the predictive functions of artificial intelligence in educational management. The research primarily focused on the potential applications of artificial intelligence in general education schools in Uzbekistan, the existing digital infrastructure, current management challenges, and the overall level of preparedness for forecasting.

The study was conducted from April–July 2025 and involved 15 state general education schools located in the Tashkent, Samarkand, and Fergana regions. In selecting the schools, the following criteria were taken into account: the number of students (schools with more than 1,000 students), the availability of digital infrastructure (OECD, 2022), and the interest of school management in artificial intelligence technologies.

A survey was conducted with 150 participants, including school principals, deputy principals, and IT professionals, to examine the current use of AI technologies, data-driven decision-making practices, and the perceived need for forecasting tools. In addition, semi-structured interviews were carried out with 20 school managers to explore implementation challenges, potential benefits, and personal insights related to the adoption of artificial intelligence.

Document analysis was conducted using EMIS data, statistical reports from regional Departments of Public Education, and school infrastructure plans. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistical techniques, including the calculation of means, percentages, and variance, as well as correlation analysis, were applied. Qualitative data were analyzed using the NVivo software through a thematic coding approach.

The findings of the study revealed three primary themes: "the need for forecasting," "uncertainty in decision-making," and "trust in artificial intelligence." All participants provided voluntary informed consent. The data were kept confidential, and the results were processed anonymously. The research was reviewed and approved by the Academic Council of the National Institute of Pedagogical Excellence named after A. A. Avloniy.

Because the study included schools from only three regions, caution should be exercised when generalizing the findings to the entire country. In addition, technical evaluations of forecasting models were not conducted within the scope of this research; however, this limitation will be addressed in future studies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The survey results indicate that 67% of school principals are familiar with the concept of artificial intelligence; however, only 18% report actively using AI or digital analytics tools in actual decision-making processes within their schools. Although many educational institutions have access to various AI-based tools, these technologies are not yet fully integrated into school management practices and are often utilized primarily for basic statistical reporting rather than for strategic planning or informed decision-making.

Table 1: AI usage status among Uzbek schools. (n=150)

AI usage status	Percentage (%)
Fully integrated	5%
Partially used	13%
Not used	82%

The table demonstrates that the adoption of artificial intelligence in school management remains highly limited. Only 5% of educational institutions have fully integrated AI tools, while 13% apply them partially. In contrast, the vast majority of schools (82%) do not use AI at all, which clearly indicates that AI implementation in Uzbekistan’s education system is still at an early stage. Source: Author’s calculations based on EMIS and survey data (2025). The survey findings further reveal that over 90% of school principals emphasized the urgent need for forecasting mechanisms supported by artificial intelligence. Respondents noted that the absence of reliable forecasting tools significantly constrains school administrators’ ability to anticipate challenges and proactively design effective solutions.

As a result, much of the current decision-making process remains reactive, with problems being addressed only after they emerge. School leaders identified several priority areas in which AI-based forecasting could have a substantial impact. One key area is student enrollment projections, as forecasting annual changes in student numbers is essential for planning classroom capacity, allocating resources efficiently, and avoiding both overcrowding and underutilization of facilities; accurate predictions would enable administrators to prepare infrastructure and staffing requirements in advance. Another critical area is teacher workforce planning, where principals stressed the importance of early planning for the opening of new classes and the recruitment of additional teachers; AI-driven models could help anticipate subject-specific or regional teacher shortages and support a more balanced distribution of human resources. Academic performance monitoring was also highlighted as a priority, particularly the prediction of declining trends in examination results; early identification of warning signals could allow timely interventions, such as remedial instruction, curriculum adjustments, or targeted student support measures.

Finally, principals underscored the need for systematic analysis of student absenteeism patterns and their underlying causes; by predicting attendance-related risks, AI systems could generate actionable insights to enhance student engagement, reduce dropout rates, and strengthen overall school performance. In summary, the responses of educational managers indicate that forecasting is not merely a supportive function but a strategic necessity within Uzbekistan’s schooling context. AI-based forecasting mechanisms have the potential to transform school governance from predominantly reactive management toward proactive planning, thereby improving system efficiency and contributing to better long-term educational outcomes.

Diagram 1: Leaders' confidence in AI-based forecasts (%)

Figure 1: Leaders' confidence in AI-based forecasting. (%)

- Expresses full confidence - 62%
- Doubtful - 25%
- Does not believe at all - 13%

Figure 1 illustrates the confidence levels of school leaders in AI-based forecasting systems. According to the survey data, 62% of respondents expressed full confidence in AI-generated predictions, indicating a strong readiness to rely on advanced technologies for decision-making in educational management, whereas 25% reported having doubts, reflecting a cautious attitude and highlighting the need for additional training and increased awareness. A further 13% of respondents stated that they do not trust AI forecasts at all, which underscores the persistence of skepticism and potential resistance to innovation within school governance structures. Overall, the findings demonstrate that although optimism toward AI-based forecasting dominates among school leaders, building institutional trust and ensuring transparency in AI systems remain critical prerequisites for their successful adoption in Uzbekistan’s education system.

Source: Author’s field survey (2025). In addition, based on the analysis of administrative documents, including EMIS data and regional statistical reports, the effectiveness of several AI-integrated forecasting models can be identified. These include regression-based prediction models used to forecast student enrollment and teacher distribution, classification models such as decision trees applied to grouping students according to their likelihood of academic success, and time-series forecasting models employed to predict classroom overloads or missed classes over time. For instance, a model developed using EMIS data for the Fergana region in 2023 assumed that the application of artificial intelligence would reduce teacher shortages by 8% compared to 2024, thereby enabling educational authorities to engage in more effective anticipatory planning.

Figure 2: Example of staffing prediction based on AI. (Fergana region, 2023-2025)

The figure compares AI-based staffing predictions with actual teacher demand for 2023-2024. In 2023, the AI model slightly underestimated teacher demand by 0.85%, with 5,800 positions predicted compared to an actual requirement of 5,850. In 2024, the model slightly overestimated demand by 0.25%, predicting 6,020 positions against an actual demand of 6,005. Despite these minor deviations, the AI-based forecasting model achieved an overall accuracy level exceeding 99% across both years, thereby demonstrating a high degree of reliability and practical suitability for forecasting staffing requirements within the education system. Source: EMIS regional data (2023-2024).

Table 2: Data analysis

Year	AI prediction	Actual need	Difference	Accuracy
2023	5,800	5,850	+50	99.1%
2024	6,020	6,005	+50	99.8%
2025	6,150	Pending	–	–

Compared with global experiences, Uzbekistan has not yet achieved broad adoption of artificial intelligence in education management; however, the growing interest among school leaders provides a strong foundation for future transformation. Moreover, the positive outlook of educational managers and system representatives toward AI and predictive technologies further reinforces the prospects for long-term development in this area. For example, in South Korea, the “Smart School System” applies AI-based solutions to predict, several months in advance, teacher demand, potential equipment shortages, and the effectiveness of teaching processes in schools. Uzbekistan similarly possesses significant potential to gradually introduce comparable AI-driven algorithms into its EMIS database, which could enable more effective planning, resource allocation, and evidence-based decision-making, ultimately leading to outcomes comparable to those observed in advanced international practices.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that although school leaders in Uzbekistan demonstrate strong interest in artificial intelligence, its practical application in forecasting and educational management remains limited. The integration of AI into the Education Management Information System (EMIS) has the potential to substantially enhance decision-making by enabling reliable predictions related to student enrollment, teacher staffing, academic performance, and attendance patterns. In this context, AI-based forecasting should be regarded not merely as a technical innovation but as a strategic instrument for improving the efficiency, equity, and overall quality of school governance. Based on the empirical findings of the study, several practical recommendations are proposed, including the gradual implementation of basic yet effective artificial intelligence models, such as systems designed to predict missed classes, as pilot initiatives within selected schools, followed by systematic testing of these models using real-world data.

In parallel, the organization of specialized advanced training programs focused on artificial intelligence and educational management is essential, with particular emphasis on equipping school principals with data-driven decision-making competencies. Further recommendations include modifying the existing EMIS architecture to incorporate AI-based forecasting models, improving analytical functionality through the integration of open APIs and data-analytics modules, and establishing annual regional forecasting indicators that focus on key variables such as absenteeism rates, teacher shortages, and student enrollment dynamics. To ensure practical impact, the use of these indicators should be formalized through mandatory procedures guiding decision-making processes at the school administration level. Finally, it is recommended to systematically examine the experiences of countries such as South Korea, Singapore, and Estonia, and to actively engage in international conferences and professional platforms related to AI-based education management, including ICAIEM, EDUCON, and EDULEARN, in order to support knowledge exchange and the adoption of international best practices.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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